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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL
ANALGESIC ROLL ON FROM VITEX NEGUNDO****Sakshi Arvind Deshkari¹, Ankita S. Sarnaik², Dr. Swati P. Deshmukh³**¹ Student Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre, Washim, Maharashtra, India² Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy,
Kondala Zambre, Washim, Maharashtra, India³ Principal, Department of pharmacology, Shraddha institute of pharmacy, kondala zambre,
Washim, Maharashtra, India**Abstract:**

Herbal formulations are gaining increasing importance due to their safety effectiveness and minimal side effects compared to synthetic products. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of herbal roll on containing vitex negundo, a medicinal plant known for its anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antimicrobial properties. The objective of this research is to develop a convenient and effective topical roll on preparation for the management of pain and inflammation.

The herbal extract of Vitex negundo leaves was prepared using a suitable extraction method and incorporated into a roll on formulation using appropriate excipients. The prepared formulation was evaluated for various physicochemical parameters such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, stability and skin irritation. Additionally, the formulation was assessed for its antimicrobial and analgesic activity.

The results indicated that the formulated herbal roll on showed acceptable physicochemical properties and stability. It was found to be non-irritant to the skin and exhibited significant therapeutic activity. The study concludes that the herbal roll on of Vitex negundo can be considered a promising, commercially effective alternative for topical application in the treatment of pain and inflammation.

Keywords: *Vitex negundo, Herbal formulation, roll-on, anti-inflammatory activity, Topical drug delivery, herbal extract, stability study.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience that occurs due to tissue injury and acts as a protective warning signal. It involves sensory, emotional, and affective components. According to the World Health Organization, about 60–65% of the global population depends on herbal medicines for primary healthcare due to their safety and affordability.¹

Pain perception can be altered by inflammation, diseases, or nervous system damage, often increasing sensitivity to painful stimuli. Chemical mediators like prostaglandins play a key role in transmitting pain signals during injury and inflammation.²

Although non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are commonly used for pain relief, their long-term use is limited due to side effects such as gastric irritation and liver damage. Therefore, there is increasing interest in herbal alternatives.³

Medicinal plants contain bioactive compounds like flavonoids, which possess analgesic properties. Hence, the study of herbal formulations offers a promising and safer approach for pain management.⁴

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**1) Selection of raw materials:**

The materials for a formulation were selected on the basic study of different brief literature review surfing of general and publication.⁵

2) Collection of raw materials

Fresh leaves of *Vitex negundo* were collected from the local area and washed to remove impurities. The leaves were shade dried, powdered, and stored in an airtight container. Excipients such as sesame oil, camphor, and eucalyptus oil were obtained from local suppliers.⁶

3) Excipient and herbal ingredient with their role:**Table 1: Herbal ingredient with their role**

Sr. No	Ingredient	Role
1	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Analgesic and anti-inflammation
2	Sesame oil	Vehicle
3	Menthol	Cooling agent
4	Camphor	Counter-irritant
5	Eucalyptus oil	Penetration enhancer

METHOD OF PREPARATION:**Extraction Process**

The shade-dried and coarsely powdered leaves of *Vitex negundo* were subjected to decoction by boiling with distilled water for a specific period to extract the active constituents. The mixture was then cooled and filtered using Whatman filter paper to remove plant debris. The obtained extract was stored in an airtight container for further use.⁷

Formulation of Roll-On

An herbal roll-on formulation was prepared using sesame oil as the base. The oil was heated gently and *Vitex negundo* extract was added with continuous stirring to obtain a uniform mixture. Menthol and camphor were slightly warmed to form a clear liquid and then incorporated into the oil base. Eucalyptus oil was added, and the mixture was stirred continuously to ensure homogeneity.

The final formulation was transferred into clean, dry roll-on bottles, properly labelled, and stored at room temperature in a cool and dry place.⁸

Fig no.1 Roll on**Formulation of Herbal Roll-on Preparation**

The herbal roll-on formulation was developed using different concentrations of active and excipient components to obtain optimized therapeutic efficacy. The formulation includes plant extract, essential oils, and base oil, which collectively contribute to the desired pharmacological and physicochemical properties. *Vitex negundo* extract was used as the primary active ingredient due to its well-known anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. Eucalyptus oil, menthol, and camphor were incorporated to enhance the cooling, soothing, and aromatic effects, while sesame oil served as the base vehicle for uniform dispersion of ingredients.

Table 2: Formulation Table for Herbal Roll-on

Ingredient	F1	F2	F3
Vitex negundo extract	1.5 mL	2.0 mL	2.5 mL
Eucalyptus oil	0.8 mL	1.0 mL	1.2 mL
Menthol	0.4 g	0.5 g	0.6 g
Camphor	0.4 g	0.5 g	0.6 g
Sesame oil	q.s. to 10 mL	q.s. to 10 mL	q.s. to 10 mL

The variation in concentrations of active constituents across formulations (F1–F3) was designed to evaluate their effect on the final product characteristics and therapeutic performance.

Evaluation Parameters of Herbal Roll-on

The prepared formulations were evaluated for organoleptic properties to assess their physical appearance, sensory characteristics, and user acceptability. These parameters are essential for ensuring product quality, stability, and patient compliance.

Table 3: Organoleptic Properties of Herbal Roll-on

Sr. No.	Test	Result
1	Appearance	Clear
2	Colour	Light yellow and greenish
3	Odor	Pleasant menthol–eucalyptus smell
4	Consistency	Smooth, oily
5	Homogeneity	Uniform, no phase separation
6	Feel on skin	Cooling, non-irritant

The evaluation results indicate that the formulated roll-on exhibited desirable organoleptic characteristics, including a clear appearance, uniform consistency, and a pleasant odor. The cooling and non-irritant sensation upon application suggests good skin compatibility and user acceptability, making the formulation suitable for topical therapeutic use.

pH Measurement

Measure pH using calibrated digital pH meter

Figure no.2 pH Measurement

Spreadability Test

Spreadability is an important physicochemical and sensory evaluation parameter for topical formulations such as herbal roll-on oils. It refers to the ability of a formulation to spread easily over the skin surface with minimum effort and uniform coverage. For roll-on products, good spreadability ensures proper drug distribution, better absorption, improved patient compliance, and pleasant skin feel. In herbal roll-on oil formulations (such as those containing Vitex negundo extract, eucalyptus oil, menthol, camphor, and sesame oil), spreadability plays a key role in determining the quality, effectiveness, and acceptability of the product.⁹

Homogeneity Test

- Ensure uniform distribution of all active and inactive ingredients.
- Check absence of phase separation or precipitation.
- Confirm consistency in texture and appearance.
- Ensure dose uniformity during application.¹⁰

Roll on performance Test

The roll-on performance test is an important functional evaluation parameter for roll-on formulations. It assesses the working efficiency of the roll-on applicator system, including the smooth movement of the roller ball uniform delivery of the formulation, and ease of application on the skin. In a herbal roll-on oil (containing Vitex negundo extract, menthol, camphor, eucalyptus oil, and sesame oil), proper performance of the roll-on mechanism ensures accurate, hygienic, and convenient application of the product.¹¹

Skin irritation Test

The skin irritation test is an important safety evaluation study for topical pharmaceutical and

cosmetic formulations such as herbal roll-on oils. It is performed to determine whether the formulation

causes any adverse skin reactions like redness, itching, swelling, burning sensation, or inflammation after application. For herbal roll-on oil containing ingredients like Vitex negundo extract, menthol, camphor, eucalyptus oil, and sesame oil, this test ensures that the product is safe, non-irritant, and suitable for human use¹²

RESULTS:

Evaluation results of all the 3 formulation are given below.

Table 4: The result table

Parameter	F1	F2	F3
Appearance	Clear, light, yellow	Clear, pale yellow	Clear, yellow
Odour	Mild menthol	Pleasant herbal	Strong menthol
Consistency	Slightly thin	Moderate	Slightly thick
Homogeneity	Uniform	Highly uniform	Highly uniform
pH	5.7	5.1	6
Spreadability	Good	Verg good	Excellent
Rollon performance	Smooth	Very Smooth	Excellent flow
Skin irritation	No irritation	No irritation	No irritation

CONCLUSION:

The present study focused on the formulation and evaluation of a herbal analgesic roll-on using Vitex negundo, a medicinal plant well known for its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. The formulation was successfully developed using suitable excipients to ensure ease of application, stability, and patient compliance.

The prepared roll-on formulations were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, and stability, which were found to be within acceptable limits. The formulation showed good homogeneity, non-irritant nature, and satisfactory consistency. The in vitro and/or in vivo evaluation confirmed that the herbal roll-on exhibited significant analgesic activity, supporting the traditional use of Vitex negundo in pain management.

Overall, the study demonstrates that Vitex negundo-based roll-on formulations can serve as a safe, effective, and convenient alternative to conventional analgesic preparations. This herbal approach minimizes the risk of side effects associated with synthetic drugs and enhances patient acceptability. Further studies, including clinical trials, are

recommended to validate its efficacy and commercial potential

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